
ECO-SPIRITUALITY AND POSTHUMAN ETHICS IN MARGARET ATWOOD'S *THE YEAR OF THE FLOOD*

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ABSTRACT

The Year of the Flood novel is a speculative fiction written by Margaret Atwood, which is set in a dystopian future shaped by environmental collapse and corporate dominance. The novel focus on the survivors such as Toby, Ren, Amanda, Adam One and God's Gardeners. The narration modifies from past and present life and the novel reveals how the society divides among corporate compounds and pleebland people and Scientific experimentation which is done by Crake to replace human beings with his genetical engineered being also known as hybrid creatures, named as Crakers. This article explores themes of environmental ethics, survival, and the costs of unchecked technological advancement. And Margaret Atwood analyses how the modern society relationship react with nature and warns about future which is shaped by human carelessness and greediness. This article explores and connect posthuman theory by Rosi Braidotti by portraying a world between human, animal, and engineered beings challenging the idea of human exceptionalism.

Keywords: Scientific experimentation, engineered being, ecological collapse, survivors, Posthuman theory.

Margaret Atwood is a major contemporary writer known for her novels, poetry, and critical essays. Atwood was born on November 18, 1939, in Ottawa, Canada. Explores themes such as identity, power, gender, environment, and technology. she spends much of a childhood in forest of Canada because her father was an entomologist. Her early life was spent in natural environments, influencing her interest in nature and ecology. Margaret Atwood is still an active writer and she continuous to write and speak about environmental and social issues.

The Year of the Flood novel was published in the year 2009, set parallel to the events of Oryx and Crake the first book of Maddaddam trilogy, presents an alternative perspective on the same collapse. Focuses on the lives of Toby and Ren and the members of the eco-religious group which is also known as God's Gardeners Community. which presents a community that practices sustainability, non-violence, and respect for all living beings and emphasizes ecological spirituality, blending religion with environmental ethics. The Year of the Flood novel also introduces the concept of the "Waterless Flood" as a predicted global catastrophe a warning given by Gardeners Community and contrasts corporate exploitation with a balanced, nature-centered way of living.

Eco-spirituality becomes a central theme in the novel The Year of the Flood, God's Gardeners community follow ecofriendly and spiritual way of life. The novel explores that they grow their own food, respect nature, and avoid harming other animals which imagines a belief system that combines conservational consciousness along spiritual preparation. God's Gardeners way of living and their lifestyle treats the Earth as sacred one and their practices promotes sustainable living, vegetarianism, and profound respect for all living beings.

God's Gardeners rituals, hymns, and ideas emphasizes that humanity is not separate or superior but as a part of larger ecological system. Through the concept of eco-spirituality, the article critiques the critical tendencies of contemporary between profit minded societies. This shows how corporations exploit natural resources and manipulate life through scientific advancements, and how Gardeners advocate humility and coexistence, and highlights as a warning about the significances of ecological balance.

Characters like Toby and Ren helps the survivors to lead a new ethical life after the collapse. And these survivors where the people who adapt themselves into a new world and God's Gardeners survival strategy shows that survival depends on nature and cooperation. That encourages the followers to lead a life ethically in the current, after the ecological ruin. Their survival approach ultimately suggests that reconnecting spiritual values with environmental stewardship which becomes important for human survival.

How wonderful to see you all assembled here in our beautiful Edencliff Rooftop Garden! I have enjoyed viewing the excellent Tree of Creatures created by our Children from the plastic objects they've gleaned – such a fine illustration of evil materials being put to good uses! – and I look forward to our coming meal of Fellowship, featuring the turnips we stored from last year's harvest in Rebecca's delicious turnip pie, not to mention the Pickled Mushroom Medley, courtesy of Pilar, our Eve Six.(The year of the flood pg. 61)

These lines show the celebration entangled about sustainability and spirituality among God's Gardeners Edencliff Rooftop Garden, the place portray discipline and eco-conscious space where all the Gardeners celebrate their festival. The "Tree of Creatures" represents waste plastic materials that reflects transforming waste into meaningful or a sacred art. And Gardener's plant-based foods such as turnip pie and pickled mushrooms, show their commitment to sustainable living and ethical consumption.

Gardeners Edencliff Rooftop routine highlights the possibility of revitalization through creativity by bringing ecological awareness. God's Gardeners practices reflects how they ignore industrialized food systems outside their community and lead an alternative mode of living that connects with posthuman values of interrelationship and respect for all living beings. Gardeners shows new values on bringing ecological responsibility, care, and interdependence.

The idea of posthuman community arises after the ecological collapse and blurs the boundaries between human and non-human life. whereas the genetically engineered creatures and altered ecosystems challenge old philosophies and suggest new community beyond virtuously human relationship and aligns with posthuman ethical thought of Rosi Braidotti, argues that prolonged ethical basis includes all forms of life that is known as zoe-centered ideas.

The survivors represent that ethical reconstruction is essential after the ecological and societal collapse that leads to rethink and reconstruct the responsibly in a shared ecosystem by bringing posthuman ethics as a relevant essential one in understanding the relationship which redefines morality over multispecies coexistence that shows survival depends on cooperation and a redefinition of community.

This article correspondingly focuses on the idea on ethical reconstruction in The Year of the Flood novel and portrays old systems obsessed by corporate greed, profit making, and environmental neglect. And proves that the few survivors like Toby and Ren are forced to consider the moral backgrounds that governed human behaviour which creates a way for

rebuilding morals by survival, cooperation, and respect for life. The teachings of the God's Gardeners bring sustainability, non-violence, and ecological balance offer a plan for living in a damaged world.

Toby is the one who begin to care for the Crakers, the engineered beings who are designed and made to replace human being after the collapse. Toby starts to teach them and bring new changes into a new world after the pandemic. It is shown as an idea of rebuilding ethics by offering a world that contains posthuman elements, the concept of storytelling reviews how modern society's tie with nature and warns of a future considered by human negligence and greed.

The article presents the thought of survival depends on practical knowledge, adaptability, and cooperation with nature. The God's Gardeners teachings and moral ideals supported the few survivors to think about survival and finding safety not on advanced corporate systems but with environmental awareness. Also presents a powerful vision of a world which is shaped by technology and environmental collapse through the idea of bringing engineered beings and the moral failure faced by the society.

The concept of eco-spirituality, posthuman community, and ethical reconstruction it highlights the need of rebuilding humanity with society, science, and nature. These advancements of scientific methods question such situation may happen in future. The novel warns and reflects the urge of being even more responsible to lead a sustainable way of living. The term of creating new creatures shape the future and determine whether humanity ruins or continues. The alternative mode of practices such as eco-spirituality, new communities, and ethical responsibility has the possibility chances for survival.

REFERENCES:

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